

Deliverable 3.1.1.1

NETWORK OF RELEVANT INDUSTRY PARTNERS

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D3.1.1.1 Network of Relevant Industry Partners

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General Information

Summary

The main objective of this deliverable is to actively involve industry stakeholders early in the platform's development to ensure its alignment with industry needs, encourage adoption, and support data sharing. By integrating feedback from these stakeholders, the project team aims to identify essential requirements and enablers that will make the platform more user-friendly and motivate partners to contribute valuable data. The scope and contributions of industry stakeholders are further detailed in [1].

This deliverable also establishes a dedicated network of industry partners, targeting organizations interested in the energy community platform, such as municipal utilities, network operators, and IT service providers. The goal is to engage at least 15 committed partners, fostering meaningful collaboration and knowledge-sharing within this network. Through workshops (as described in D3.1.2.1 and [2]) and surveys, these partners provide expert insights that are essential for co-developing platform requirements. The initial set of requirements will later be refined, as outlined in D3.1.2.2.

Additionally, this work connects to D2.1.1.1, contributing to the categorization of industry stakeholders and an initial evaluation of their roles and involvement on the platform. This network of engaged industry partners not only supports platform development but also lays the groundwork for ongoing industry engagement and input.

Related Deliverables: D2.1.1.1; D3.1.2.1; D3.1.2.2

Deliverable within NFDI4Energy

Figure 1 - Task Area 3 connections to other Task Areas within the NFDI4Energy consortium.

This deliverable covers the following tasks, as part of M3.1, illustrated in Fig.1:

- Identify relevant industry partners for the NFDI4Energy platform,
- Establish a network of at least 15 industry partners who are committed to contributing to the NFDI4Energy project through participation in workshops and surveys,
- Describe the industry partner network.

Deliverable

1. Process of Network Acquisition

As an initial step, we defined the scope of "energy-related industry." As detailed in D2.1.1.1, this definition encompasses the following categories:

- Energy producers,
- Energy suppliers,
- Network operators,
- Technology providers,
- IT companies,
- Consulting firms.

Within the NFDI4Energy consortium, we initiated outreach by creating and distributing a survey to industry contacts across all consortium partners and further shared it via LinkedIn. The survey centered on the concept of open data, a well-known topic in the industry, and one that aligns closely with the anticipated contributions of industry partners to the FAIR research platform we are developing.

The survey received 13 responses, which are visualized in Section 2. Through this survey and additional outreach efforts, including participation in energy-related conferences, we successfully engaged 18 network members who have committed to supporting platform development by participating in surveys and workshops.

2. Interest in the Concept of Opening Up Industry Data: Survey Results

Survey Participants (n=13)

Figure 2 - How survey participants categorize their companies' activities.

Figure 3 - Experience level of survey participants in the energy field.

Survey Results

Figure 4 - Survey answers to the statement "Open data concepts have potential for the energy sector" (n=13).

As shown in Fig. 4, most participants see significant potential in open data. Their perspectives were elaborated through free-text responses, providing insights into both optimistic and skeptical viewpoints.

Optimistic Views on Open Data

Based on free-text answers, participants highlighted several benefits:

1. **Accelerating Digitalization and Innovation**
 "Without open data, full-scale digitalization is not feasible."
 Open data is seen as essential for advancing digitalization in the energy sector, enabling innovation, streamlining research, and fostering technologies to improve energy efficiency and renewable management.
2. **Supporting Collaboration and Reducing Redundancies**
 "Easy and transparent access to up-to-date insights accelerates progress, reduces duplication, and decreases errors."
 Open data facilitates collaboration, reducing redundant efforts and errors, and promoting a more efficient approach to industry challenges.
3. **Improving Forecasting and Planning**
 "Increases planning security for demand and generation."
 Access to open data enhances planning for energy demand and supply, helping stakeholders better optimize resources and manage fluctuations, particularly crucial for renewable integration.

Skeptical Views on Open Data

Some free-text responses highlighted potential drawbacks:

1. **Data Privacy and Security Concerns**
 "Our clients, electricity distribution network operators, operate critical infrastructure and are hardly willing to share any data."
 The risks of exposing vulnerabilities or compromising security make operators of critical infrastructure wary of open data.
2. **Commercial Interests and Proprietary Data**
 "Some applications face data protection challenges; companies also want to use/market data themselves."

Many companies view their data as a competitive asset and prefer to control or monetize it, limiting their willingness to share openly.

3. Interoperability and Data Fragmentation

“Currently, data is very scattered, proprietary, and heterogeneous. Large, reliable datasets are needed for digitalization and optimization.”

Fragmented, non-standardized data complicates leveraging open data at scale, reducing its practical utility.

The survey results show a clear divide between the optimism about the potential benefits of open data and the concerns over practical challenges and risks. Optimistic responses focus on open data's potential to accelerate digitalization, foster collaboration, and improve efficiency and transparency. Participants recognize that access to open data can drive innovation, facilitate better planning, and create synergies across the energy sector, especially in areas like renewables and integrated energy management.

On the skeptical side, respondents raise valid concerns about data security, privacy, and the proprietary nature of data. For operators of critical infrastructure, open data may pose security risks. Additionally, the commercial value of proprietary data makes companies hesitant to share it openly, as they would prefer to retain control for competitive advantage. Technical issues, such as fragmented data and interoperability challenges, further complicate efforts to standardize and integrate open data on a large scale.

In summary, while there is a shared belief in the transformative potential of open data, practical and regulatory barriers will need to be addressed. Solutions like secure data-sharing frameworks, privacy-preserving technologies, and interoperability standards could help reconcile these viewpoints, allowing open data to fulfil its potential while managing risks effectively.

Figure 5 - Answers (multiple answers possible) on most important needs in open data platforms (n=13).

The survey results reveal a preference among participants for simulation tools and data analysis capabilities on open data platforms (see Fig. 5), with 11 out of 13 participants identifying this as their most important need. This indicates that stakeholders view analytics and simulation tools as crucial for deriving insights, optimizing processes, and supporting decision-making in the energy sector. The next highest priority is data provision, with 9 participants emphasizing the importance of contributing their own data to the platform. This suggests a willingness within the industry to share data, potentially to facilitate collaborative projects or to enhance the richness of the available data pool. However, only 6 participants highlighted data access as a key need, which may imply that while access to data is valued, there is a stronger focus on tools that transform raw data into actionable insights. These responses suggest that an effective open data platform in the energy sector should prioritize robust analytical and simulation capabilities, supported by a collaborative environment for data sharing.

3. Network Overview

Figure 6 - Categorization of our industry networks activities.

The industry network established through our survey and outreach efforts now includes 18 partners committed to platform development through survey and workshop participation. This network represents a diverse range of stakeholders (see Fig. 6): 23% are technology providers, 38% are IT companies, 31% are energy suppliers, and 8% operate as both technology providers and IT companies. This diversity brings expertise across technical infrastructure, software solutions, energy supply, providing a robust foundation for platform functionality and sector relevance.

However, the current composition indicates a need to enhance perspectives from network operators and energy producers. While IT companies contribute heavily to digitalization and data solutions, supporting our goals for simulation tools and analytics, and energy suppliers ensure the platform aligns with industry-specific needs by integrating real-world energy data, network operators and energy producers could add critical insights, especially regarding regulatory compliance and data standards. Both groups often navigate regulatory demands and complex data interoperability challenges, making them valuable contributors to platform standards and regulatory alignment.

In conclusion, while the current network composition provides a strong foundation, expanding representation from network operators and energy producers would improve the platform’s applicability across the energy sector. This network is expected to evolve throughout the project’s development, adapting to emerging needs to ensure comprehensive support and relevance as the platform advances.

References

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